

The Three Petro-Pigs

Three petro-pigs prospected Earth's combustible resources array,
and they extracted and plotted to make everyone else pay,
They dug and extracted from other peoples' lands with greed,
And they lobbied governments to keep society in need.

The petro-pigs sold millions of tonnes of coal, making carbon emissions soar,
they profited and they profited extracting more and more.
They lobbied every day to get taxpayers funds to subsidize their score,
then an awakening society finally saw...

"Petro-pig, petro-pig won't you please stop this coal extracting and burning?"
"No, no, no, not by the bottom-line on my winny, win, win."
"But then climate change will huff and It'll puff and It'll blow our houses in."
"No, no, no, awakening society, petrostates will not let you win."

So climate change huffed,
and climate change puffed,
and climate change blew societies' houses in

The second petro-pigs built their riches on crude oil rigs,
they broadcast false negative propaganda about clean energy gigs,
With curtains on the truth and explosions on the seafloor,
then an awakening society finally saw...

"Petro-pig, petro-pig we must stop your crude oil extraction and carbon emissions"
"No, no, no, not by the power of oil companies financial winny, win, wins."
"But then extreme floods and storms will huff and they'll puff and they'll blow all our infrastructure in."
"No, no, no, awakening society, petrostates will not let you win."

So extreme floods and storms huffed,
and they puffed,
and blew societies' infrastructure in

The third petro-pigs built a wealth empire out of gas tricks,
Gas companies bought off governments to play politics,
They made up a fib that gas use lowers your energy bill,
When in fact they were just robbing the taxpayer's till.

"Petro-pig, petro-pig your methane emission profiteering is clearly a sin"
"No, no, no, you're not touching the extraordinary margin on our winny, win, win."
"But then heat, drought and fire will huff and puff and blow societies' lives in."
"No, no, no, awakening society, petrostates will not let you win."

So heat, drought and fire huffed,
and it puffed,
and it blew societies' lives in

Now the three petro-pigs each had impenetrable wealth and power,
so they wouldn't have to worry about governments or societies going sour.
They each funded campaigns so they could continue to win,
and soon our one and only planet Earth was tossed in the bin.